

APPROACHES AND METHODS OF TEACHING THE ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Annotation: One of the central topics in language education that has been extensively debated over the years is the grammar of foreign languages. The perspective on grammar has shaped the characteristics of various teaching methods, influencing the principles and techniques employed in instruction. This paper explores the primary approaches to teaching English grammar, identifies the leading methodologies in contemporary English language instruction, and discusses the key methods they implement.

Keywords: English grammar instruction, modern verb forms, tense categories, types and voice, teaching principles and methods.

The training of future English teachers in our country is being aligned with international qualification standards, drawing on advanced foreign practices to cultivate specialists capable of fluent communication in foreign languages. This has established a foundational framework for enhancing the contributions of global civilization.

The "Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" emphasizes the need to enhance the quality and effectiveness of higher education institutions by adopting international educational standards and evaluating educational quality. Consequently, this has broadened the scope for integrating language instruction into various disciplines within higher education. Additionally, the Presidential Resolution of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 (PQ-5117) highlights the necessity for proficiency at the B1-B2 levels, as outlined in this directive [1, 2].

One of the most significant challenges in teaching English grammar lies in mastering verb tenses. Students often struggle with grammatical verb forms due to a lack of clarity regarding time, type, and associated categories. Therefore, it is essential to examine the methods and approaches used in teaching English grammar, identify common difficulties students encounter with verb tenses, analyze typical errors they make, and explore modern techniques and exercises that can address these issues.

Introducing the temporal system of English verbs and utilizing foundational concepts during instruction can enhance students' mastery of English, encourage communication in foreign language classes, focus attention on new material, and promote critical thinking skills.

The relevance of this article stems from the insufficient development of instructional materials aimed at effectively addressing challenges related to the application of English verb tenses in spoken communication.

The approaches and methods for teaching English, like those for any foreign language, are continually evolving as our understanding of language nature and study methods progresses. This adaptation will fulfill the global demand for more effective educational programs in institutions worldwide.

English is widely used across geographical boundaries, facilitating its use both domestically and internationally. The number of individuals who speak English as a foreign language is steadily increasing, with non-native speakers now outnumbering native speakers in many contexts.

A foreign language is one that is infrequently utilized in a learner's immediate social environment. It may be relevant for future travel or other intercultural exchanges. It is typically taught as either a mandatory subject or an optional course but is not immediately applied in practice [6].

When discussing methods, it is crucial to distinguish between the theoretical philosophy of language teaching and the practical procedures derived from it. Precision is essential in grammar instruction, and errors should be avoided at all costs.

Situational language learning activities are integral to a set of standardized procedures endorsed by many contemporary educators. Textbooks that incorporate situational language learning remain prevalent globally. This method continues to be favored because its principles resonate with the instincts of many practice-oriented teachers, emphasizing oral practice, grammar, and sentence structures.

Given the importance of structure in language, initial instruction should prioritize mastering grammatical frameworks. Verbal literacy encompasses accuracy in pronunciation, grammar, and the ability to respond swiftly and clearly in spoken situations. Teaching listening, pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary focuses on developing fluent speech. While reading and writing skills can also be taught, they largely depend on already established oral competencies. Language fundamentally revolves around speech, and the ability to communicate effectively relies on correctly understanding and reproducing the essential phonological features of the target language, fluently using basic grammatical structures in conversation, and possessing sufficient vocabulary to facilitate speech.

The role of English grammar has sparked intense debate over the years. In the modern era, the significance of grammar in foreign language instruction has fluctuated frequently, sometimes increasing or decreasing in prominence. Recently, there has been a trend toward diminishing the role of grammar, resulting in a notable rise in errors within student speech.

On one hand, efforts to eliminate grammar entirely or to overemphasize its importance can adversely affect practical language proficiency. The question of grammar's role and extent within an English course is not isolated; it varies across languages. In contrast to Russian courses, where grammar holds a primary status as both a theoretical and practical discipline fostering mental development, the English grammar framework should not merely aim at mastering grammatical rules but also support broader educational objectives.

Analysis of various English grammars leads to a clear conclusion: English grammar exhibits a distinctly descriptive linguistic (and non-communicative) orientation, as evidenced by its theoretical presentations, tasks, and types of exercises. For instance, "There are various types of predicates in English that differ in structure (simple versus compound) and composition (compound nominal versus compound verb). A compound nominal predicate consists of an aspectual verb alongside a full-value verb." Additionally, "The main verbs in English include: to begin, to continue, to finish," among others. Often, foreign language grammars do not effectively serve practical learning goals. Information regarding spontaneous parts of speech or types of predicates—similar to tasks focused on identifying, memorizing, and reproducing grammatical constructs—fails to cultivate speech skills related to specific linguistic mechanisms and concepts.

Vitlin J.L. outlines certain conditions he deems essential for successfully achieving practical language proficiency:

- 1) It is crucial to enhance differentiation in selecting materials for active versus passive grammatical minimums while employing diverse teaching methods to master these minimums (considering the unique characteristics of the students' native language). The formation of active grammatical minimum rules should particularly highlight common ways of expressing ideas in the mother tongue using the lexical and grammatical resources of the foreign language. Conversely, students must be guided on how to comprehend grammatical forms they encounter in foreign texts but may not utilize in their own speech.

- 1) It is essential to reevaluate the use of grammatical terminology in foreign language instruction. To enhance grammar teaching, it is recommended to

develop new textbooks for higher education that reduce the reliance on grammatical terms. These textbooks should include a concise glossary with explanatory examples.

2) Addressing the selection of grammatical topics in foreign language textbooks and curricula for various educational institutions is also necessary.

3) There should be a significant shift in the traditional presentation of grammatical content and the language used in teaching students who lack a background in linguistics. Grammar, including its theoretical aspects, can be delivered in an engaging and dynamic manner; it should be emotionally stimulating, student-centered, entertaining, and complemented by visuals. A considerable amount of research has focused on approaches and methods for teaching grammar. Traditionally, educators have identified two primary approaches: explicit and implicit. The explicit approach involves teaching grammatical rules and explaining grammatical concepts. In contrast, the implicit approach relies on repetition and memorization of grammatically correct structures without direct instruction of the underlying rules.

The explicit method can be implemented in two main ways: inductively, where students analyze language examples to discover grammatical patterns and formulate rules; and deductively, where the teacher presents the grammatical rule first, followed by opportunities for students to practice new structures communicatively.

The inductive method is particularly beneficial for cognitive development and fostering self-directed learning strategies among students. Material that is discovered through exploration tends to be retained more effectively. However, despite its advantages, the inductive method demands significantly more time and effort from educators, making it impractical as the sole approach in current foreign language teaching contexts at secondary schools and universities.

Grammar teaching methods are guided by several well-established principles. One key principle is sequential learning, where grammatical concepts are introduced in a specific order. For example, the continuous tense is typically taught after the present tense, followed by the perfect continuous tense. Similarly, tenses are introduced before passive voice and indirect speech. It is clear that variations in this sequence exist.

When considering grammatical competence as an intuitive understanding developed through complex social and cognitive activities, grammar instruction aligns with a communicative approach. This perspective posits that grammar acquisition occurs through solving communicative challenges, emphasizing the

practical use of forms in speech. This approach is regarded as more effective than traditional methods, which focus on imparting a fixed set of knowledge to specific student groups within defined learning environments. The traditional approach often aims at memorizing numerous rules, exceptions, categories, and paradigms without fostering independent adaptation of these rules to real-life speech situations.

Conversely, the second approach to teaching English grammar emphasizes the semantic aspects of language use. Relying solely on form-focused learning can hinder the development of communicative competence.

Skills and competencies in language learning are often developed through the repetition and memorization of forms used in various speech contexts. The formation of grammatical expressions, however, occurs when learners adapt these forms to specific speech situations. Consequently, both approaches rely on just one of the potential mechanisms for developing grammatical competence: the first approach emphasizes passive conscious assimilation, while the second focuses on unconscious assimilation.

In contemporary foreign language education, the communicative and cognitive approaches are considered paramount. The communicative approach entails a comprehensive systematization of the relationships among various components of the learning content. These components include: a general operating system; systems for speech activity and communication; the structure of the English language; deliberate comparative analysis between students' native languages and English; mechanisms of speech (such as production, perception, and interaction); systems of textual speech products; structural speech forms (including dialogues, monologues, and various message types); and the overall learning system for the

English language. This holistic approach results in the development of a systemic understanding of English as a means of communication in its broadest context.

The cognitive approach to grammar instruction encourages teachers to activate students' cognitive processes and to facilitate independent reflective activities. This leads to comparative analysis, comprehension, memorization, mastery, and appropriate use of grammatical structures in communication. However, traditional grammar exercises are not suitable for this method. Key aspects of the cognitive approach include:

- A heightened expectation for textual materials that provide students with ample opportunities to observe how the targeted language phenomena operate and to discern their governing principles.
- Teachers should leverage a wide array of cognitive strategies in the classroom to stimulate students' reflective engagement.
- A structured set of exercises should be developed to enhance students' conceptual understanding of language facts and to cultivate strategies for grasping grammatical concepts, taking into account the stages of human knowledge acquisition.

In conclusion, English grammar has long been a focal point of discussion within language education. Various methods exist for teaching foreign languages, with educators traditionally differentiating between explicit and implicit approaches. In today's context, the communicative and cognitive approaches stand out as effective means of engaging students' cognitive processes, fostering independent reflective activities, and enabling successful mastery and application of foreign grammatical structures. Understanding the nuances of grammatical categories such as time, aspect, and voice is essential for clearly explaining how these forms function. The cognitive perspective views grammatical structures as a means for expressing and storing knowledge within the language system.

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